

EXPERIENCE IN TREATMENT OF CAPTIVE LIONS, COUGARS AND BEARS WITH ASCARID INFECTIONS: A REVIEW

Mariana Panayotova-Pencheva

Institute of Experimental Morphology, Pathology and Anthropology with Museum, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Sofia, Bulgaria
E-mail: marianaspa@abv.bg

ABSTRACT

Parasite control in captive animals is often difficult and have a row of specificities. Ascarid infections are among the most common parasitoses in animals, especially for captive ones. The aim of this study was to review the experience in treatment of ascaridosis in lions, cougars and bears. Drugs, dosages and schemes of treatment are presented. Bibliographic reference showed that over the years piperazine, pyrantel pamoate, benzimidazoles and ivermectin were the most used medicines to treat *Toxascaris leonina* in lions and cougars and *Baylissascariasis* spp. infections in bears. Based on the summarized data fenbendazole applying in extended schedules or a dosage of 15 mg/kg body weight could be recommended for treatment of ascarid infections in bears, and ivermectin at a dose of 0.2–0.3 mg/kg body weight twice in four weeks interval could be recommended for treatment of ascarid infections in lions. Combined preparations of drugs from different pharmaceutical groups have also shown high efficiency and can be successfully used in such cases.

Key words: anthelmintics; ascaridosis; bears; *Panthera leo*; *Puma concolor*.

Introduction

Parasitoses in animals, including the wild ones, display an array of negative effects. Most of them become a pre-disposing factor for secondary deficiencies and infections, others are detrimental to reproduction and some would lead to lethality of the hosts. On the other hand when wild animals are in close contact with humans, as in zoos for instance, they are often an important source of hazardous parasitic zoonoses. Therefore, taking measures to combat parasitic diseases in the wild animals inhabit places such as zoos, rescue centers, reserves and others, is an indicator not only of good governance of these shelters, but is also necessary condition for human health.

Parasite control is one of the pillars of the preventive health care of zoo animals (Kvapil et al., 2017). Its implementation should be routine, involving a number of stages, including appropriate antiparasitic treatment. The choice and use of antiparasitic drugs in zoo animals however have their own specificities. In most cases, the medicines on the market are designed for domestic animals. This necessitates that dosage and application methods be adapted for use in zoos, which itself carries certain risks. In this connection it would be useful to take into account the previous experience in treatment of the particular infections in different animal species, including types of drugs and treatment regimens. The reference to previous experience would also help with reducing the drug resistance appearing after untimely and/or unnecessary antiparasitic treatments and would improve the parasite control in the zoological gardens.

Recently we found and treated some nematode infections in carnivores from the Sofia Zoo (Panayotova-Pencheva and Dakova, 2022). This, as well as the peculiarities in the control of wild animal parasitoses, provoked us to carry out the present study. Its goal was to review the experience in the treatment of the found infections, namely toxascaridosis in lions and cougars, and ascaridosis in bears. To achieve the goal reference was made both on available librarian sources and Internet

databases through combinations of keywords such *Toxascaris leonina*, Ascaridae, lion, cougar, bear, treatment, *Panthera leo*, *Puma concolor*, *Ursus arctos* and others.

Results and Discussion

The performed literature reference showed that over the years, piperazine, pyrantel pamoate, benzimidazoles and ivermectin have been the most used medicines to treat *T. leonina* in lions and cougars, as well as ascarid infections in bears (Table 1). Piperazine was marketed as an anthelmintic in the early 20th century (<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Piperazine>). It has been widely used in veterinary medicine for decades. In the initial period of its use, it was found to be effective in zoo bears with *Toxascaris transfuga* infection (Mirolyubov, 1961), especially when combined with niclosamide (Mastacan *et al.*, 1969). About 30 years later, its use in zoo lions with *T. leonina* infection led to only temporary improvement, despite being administered at a much higher dose (Sayid & Mohammed, 1997–1998). In the early 21st century, the failure of piperazine at an even higher dose to adequately treat *T. leonina* infection in lions demonstrated the development of drug resistance (Kumar *et al.*, 2005).

Table 1: Literature data about treatment of ascarid infections in lions, cougars and bears; chronologically

A	P	Drug, Dosage and Scheme of Treatment	Results and Conclusions	Source
B	<i>T.t.</i>	Piperazine adipate - 0.025 g/kg bw	It has been effective.	Mirolyubov (1961)
PB	<i>T.t.</i>	Regular treatment over a year with piperazine adipate at 0.1 to 0.2 mg/kg bw and niclosamide (2 to 3 g)	It has been apparently successful.	Mastacan <i>et al.</i> (1969)
B	<i>B.t.</i>	Dichlorvos*	It has reduced EPG to zero in many bear species 1-2 days after treatment, however, these animals have become reinfected within months after treatment.	Experience from 1969: Sapp <i>et al.</i> (2017)
PB	<i>B.t.</i>	Mebendazole	Coprological examinations have been negative after 4 -7 days from the beginning of the treatment.	Papini <i>et al.</i> (1994)
	<i>T.l.</i>	Thiabendazole boluses (10 g bolus for 150 kg bw, p.o. with meat) in two doses 28 days apart	Incomplete cure.	
L	<i>T.l.</i>	Piperazine dihydrochloride (100 mg/kg bw, p.o. in drinking water) in three consecutive doses 28 days apart	Improvement of the animals' condition and reduction of EPG. However, two months later EPG has risen again.	Sayid and Mohammed (1997–1998)
	<i>T.l.</i>	Ivermectin in 2 separate doses 28 days apart: 2.5 ml/kg bw, in drinking water	This scheme plus direct flaming of the floor and troughs, has been effective, even in persistent infections.	
L	<i>T.l.</i>	Piperazine - 220 mg/kg bw, p.o. Ivermectin - 0.2 mg/kg bw, s.c., twice at one week interval	Piperazine resistance has been established. Ivermectin has been 100% effective.	Kumar <i>et al.</i> (2005)
L	<i>T.l.</i>	Pyrantel pamoate - 10 mg/kg bw Metronidazole - 3 g/animal x 3 days	Reduction in EPG to zero 5-15 days after treatment. But, there has been reappearance of eggs after a month of treatment.	Singh <i>et al.</i> (2006)
L	<i>T.l.</i>	During the three year period: Ivermectin (0.2 mg/kg) twice in the first year, and once in the second year Piperazine citrate (110 mg/kg) twice at an interval of four weeks in the third year	<i>T.l.</i> and <i>Toxocara sp.</i> was persistent during the three year research, which was a sign that the applied treatment schedule was not sufficient.	Atanaskova <i>et al.</i> (2011)
L	<i>T.l.</i>	Pyrantel pamoate - 20 mg/kg bw; Levamisole - 4.4 mg/kg bw; Ivermectin - 0.3 mg/kg bw. All with meat.	Reappearance of infection occurred 24, 45 and 52 days after administration of pyrantel pamoate, levamisole and ivermectin, respectively.	Dehuri <i>et al.</i> (2013)

A	P	Drug, Dosage and Scheme of Treatment	Results and Conclusions	Source
SB	<i>B.t.</i>	Fenbendazole - 10 mg/kg bw for three consecutive days, associated with complete disinfection of the enclosures	The result could be considered as treatment failure.	Moudgil et al. (2014)
		The initial treatment with fenbendazole at 15 mg/kg bw for first three days has been extended for another three days with a dose rate of 10 mg/kg bw	This scheme has proved to be effective with zero EPG on days 1, 4, 7 and 21 after treatment.	
L	<i>T.l.</i>	Fenbendazole - 10 mg/kg bw, once daily for three days.	Ineffective scheme with maximum EPG reduction of 69.35% (on the 3 day) and 51.61% (on the 21 day) after treatment.	Moudgil et al. (2016)
		Fenbendazole with extended period dose schedule - 5 days at 10 mg/kg bw.	Maximum EPG reduction of 95.34% on the 7 day after treatment.	
		Ivermectin - 100 µg/kg bw.	EPG reduction of 95.74% on the 7 day after treatment.	
L	<i>T.l.</i>	Pyrantel pamoate – 5 mg/kg bw for 3 consecutive days.	No eggs of the parasite have been found on the 7, 14t and 30 day after treatment.	Alexander et al. (2017)
L; C	<i>T.l.</i>	Praziquantel + pyrantel pamoate (Tablets Pratel®) - 1 tablet per 10 kg bw once or twice with an interval of 14 days, p.o. with food	Complete release of animals from <i>T.l.</i> and <i>T.m.</i> (on the 10, 20 and 30 day after treatment).	Ponomarenko et al. (2017)
	<i>T.m.</i>	Praziquantel + pyrantel embonate + fenbendazole (Tablets Cestal plus®) - 1 tablet per 10 kg bw, once or twice with an interval of 14 days, p.o. with food		
B	<i>B.sp.</i>	Ivermectin - 0.3 mg/kg bw; Fenbendazole - 10 mg/kg bw	Full disposal of worms from the animals has been achieved with ivermectin. Efficiency of fenbendazole has been lower.	(Shuleshko et al. (2017).
B	<i>B.sp.</i>	Fenbendazole, Mebendazole and Dichlorvos*	Results have been not promising.	Sheikh et al. (2018)
L	<i>T.l.</i>	A combination of oxcyclozanide 6% and levamisole 3% at the rate of 1ml per 4 kg bw.	EPG has been reduced to zero on the 3, 7, 10 and 21 days after treatment.	Ganager et al. (2019)
C	<i>T.l.</i>	Febantel - twice with an interval of 14 days.	Quarterly dehelminthization alone is not a sufficient measure to free animals from infection.	Panova and Khrustalev (2020)
L	<i>T.l.</i>	Milbemycin oxime + praziquantel (Milprazon 12.5 mg/125 mg tablets for dogs weighing at least 5 kg®) – 4 tablets p.o. with food	Negative fecal tests on the 7, 30 and 60 day after treatment.	Panayotova-Pencheva and Dakova (2022)
C	<i>T.l.</i>	Milbemycin oxime + praziquantel (Milprazon 12.5 mg/125 mg tablets for dogs weighing at least 5 kg®) – 2 tablets p.o. with food	Negative fecal test on the 7 day after treatment. Infection reappearance 30 days after treatment.	
C	<i>T.l.</i>	Praziquantel 50mg+ pyrantel embonate 144mg +fenbendazole 200mg (Cestal plus®) – 2 tablets p.o. with food	Negative fecal test 60 days after treatment.	
BB		Ivermectin + praziquantel (Noromectin Praziquantel Duo, 18.7 mg/g + 140.3 mg/g Oral Paste for Horses®) – 2 syringes p.o. with food	Negative fecal tests on the 7, 30 and 60 day after treatment.	

A – animals; P – parasite; B – bears; BB – brown bear; PB – polar bears; L – lions; SB - sloth bears; C – cougars; *T.t.* – *Toxascaris transfuga*; *T.l.* – *Toxascaris leonina*; *T.m.* – *Toxocara mistax*; *U.s.* – *Uncinaria stenocephala*; *B.t.* – *Baylissascariasis transfuga*; *B.sp.* – *Baylissascariasis sp.*; EPG – egg count per gram of feces; *Banned for use in the European Union since 2012

Administration of pyrantel pamoate in a single dose of 10-20 mg/kg body weight (bw) in lions with *T. leonina* infection resulted in a short-term effect, lasting about one month (Singh *et al.*, 2006). Its application at a lower dose for three days showed better results (Alexander *et al.*, 2017). According to Alexander *et al.* (2017) oral baiting of large quantity of dewormers such as pyrantel palmoate in meat would be lead to rejection of the meat by the lions. For this reason, these authors followed

a treatment protocol of lower dose but longer duration in order to increase the palatability of the baited meat.

Short-term antiparasitic efficacy of pyrantel pamoate at a dose of 20 mg/kg bw in lions was also established by Dehuri et al. (2013): reappearance of *T. leonina* and *Ancylostoma* sp. infections was observed 24 days post treatment. During this experiment levamisole at a dose of 4.4 mg/kg bw gave a slightly better effect: *T. leonina* and *Ancylostoma* sp. infections reappeared on days 45 and 31 after treatment, respectively.

Sayid & Mohammed (1997–1998) used thiabendazole boluses (10 g bolus for 150 kg bw, p.o. with meat, in two doses 28 days apart) to treat *T. leonina* infection in lions, but have not achieved complete cure.

Therapeutic treatment of *B. transfuga* infection in a sloth bear with fenbendazole has been tried by Moudgil et al. (2014). The bear has showed high egg count per gram of feces (EPG) (2800) before the therapeutic intervention. The regular deworming strategy (i.e. with fenbendazole at a dose of 10 mg/kg bw for 3 consecutive days) has been little effective with reduction of EPG from 2800 (day zero) to 400, 700 and 800 on the 1, 4 and 7 day after treatment respectively. An increased EPG value of 2400 (6 times) has been recorded on day 21 post treatment with respect to day 1. According to the authors, this result could be considered as treatment failure, due to development of tolerance or resistance. This could be attributed either to repeated use of lower dose fenbendazole (7.5mg/kg bw) as an anthelmintic in the bears over a long period prior to the study, or to ineffective drug dosage due to the bear failing to consume the whole therapeutic dose. Because of the failure to completely treatment, a modified schedule has been opted with an increased dose and period of treatment (i.e. for 6 consecutive days at a dose of 15 mg/kg bw for the first three days followed by 10 mg/kg bw for the next three days). This modified schedule has proved to be effective, with EPG values of zero observed on days 1, 4, 7 and 21 after the last day of treatment, which according to Moudgil et al. (2014) has shown development of resistance. The authors consider that the resistance against benzimidazoles develops in stages and that the individual parasites respond to repeated doses of the drug, as has been observed in their study. The conclusion about development of benzimidazole resistance has been confirmed by the same researchers in a study concerning lions. In it the effectiveness of fenbendazole against *T. leonina* infections has been improved with administration for five days rather than three (Moudgil et al., 2016).

Brown bears from a private zoo collection spontaneously infected with *Baylissascaris transfuga* were dewormed with fenbendazole at a dose of 10 mg/kg bw (Shuleshko et al., 2017). Positive effect from application of the drug was observed – the number of eggs in one microscope field of view fell significantly during the treatment. However, full disposal of worms was not detected: extensity efficiency was 33.3%, while intensity efficiency was 85.7%.

Sayid & Mohammed (1997–1998) have treated *T. leonina* infested lions with ivermectin in the form of the preparation for sheep Oramec-drench®. They used 2 separate doses at 2.5 ml/kg bw in drinking water, 28 days apart. Complete clearance of infection after the third day of treatment were achieved. The animals have continued to be negative in parasitological examination up to 28 day after the first dose as well as two months after the second dose. Sayid & Mohammed (1997–1998) concluded that ivermectin in this scheme, addition to direct flaming of the floor and troughs, is effective against *T. leonina* in lions, even in case of persistent infections.

Kumar et al. (2005) also found 100% effectiveness of ivermectin using at a dose of 0.2 mg/kg bw, sc, twice at one week interval in lions parasitized with *T. leonina*.

Atanaskova et al. (2011) have treated *Toxocara* sp. infection in lions from Zoological Garden in Skopje with ivermectin in 2 consecutive years. The drug has been administrated at a dose of 0.2 mg/kg twice in the first year, and once in the second year. Despite treatment, the worming continued to persist. The authors commented that though it is possible the animals have been parasite free immediately after treatment, obviously the preventive measures applied during this period have not been sufficient or there was a high rate of reinfection.

Of the three tested drugs pyrantel pamoate, levamisole and ivermectin, the last one administered at a dose of 0.3 mg/kg bw had the longest lasting effect against nematode infestations in lions (Dehuri et al. 2013). Ivermectin reduced the fecal egg count of *T. leonina* and *Ancylostoma* sp. to 100% on 3 day post treatment. The reappearance of these infections occurred on the 52 and 45 days post-treatment respectively, whereas after treatment with the other drugs this occurred significantly earlier.

Experiencing different schemes of treatment of *T. leonina* infection in lions Moudgil et al. (2016) found greater efficacy of ivermectin (0.1 mg/kg bw) over fenbendazole. However, they did not observe 100% efficacy soon after deworming as in the previous studies – the EPG reduction has been 95.74% seven days after treatment. This is probably due to the lower dose of ivermectin applied (0.1 mg/kg bw) compared to that used in the previous studies (Sayid & Mohammed, 1997–1998; Kumar et al., 2005; Dehuri et al. 2013).

Greater efficacy of ivermectin over fenbendazole was also found by Shuleshko *et al.* (2017) who treated brown bears, infected with *B. transfuga*. Ivermectin applied at a dose of 0.3 mg/kg bw achieved full disposal of animals from worms. Both extensity and intensity efficiency of this drug constituted 100%.

A couple of publications reported treatment of ascarids in lions, cougars and bears with combined antiparasitic preparations. Ponomarenko et al. (2017) performed two experiments on the therapeutic efficacy of Pratel® (containing praziquantel and pyrantel pamoate) and Cestal plus® (containing praziquantel, pyrantel embonate, and fenbendazole) against intestinal nematodes of carnivores from a zoo in Kharkiv. Pratel® at a dose of 1 tablet per 10 kg bw once or twice (with an interval of 14 days) was given for therapeutic purposes of lions and cougars in the first experiment. The necessary amount of the preparation was placed inside the meat, in which several incisions were made and fed in the morning. According to the results of the experiment, single and double use of the drug led to the complete release of experimental animals from *T. leonina* and *Toxocara mistax*. Examination of feces for the presence of eggs of intestinal nematodes, which was carried out on the 10, 20 and 30 day after treatment, showed absence of these ascarids, i.e. the effectiveness of Pratel® in the tested dose was 100%. In the second experiment carnivores were individually treated with Cestal plus® puted in meat at a dose of one tablet per 10 kg bw once or twice (with an interval of 14 days). This preparation has been also 100% effective both in single or double administration against *T. leonina* and *T. mistax* in lions and cougars.

Ganager et al. (2019) have tried the effectiveness of the ruminant dewormer Neozide plus suspension® (combination of oxcyclozanide 6% and levamisole 3%) over the lions from 3 Indian parks. Before deworming 60% of animals have been positive for eggs of *T. leonina*. This medicine at the rate of 1ml per 4 kg bw revealed EPG reducing to zero on subsequent 3, 7, 10 and 21 days post treatment and proved to be 100% effective.

Results of Panayotova-Pencheva & Dakova (2022) confirmed the trend macrocyclic lactones and combined preparations of several drugs being high effective against ascarids in the target ani-

mals. *Toxascaris leonina* infested lion and cougar were treated with a combined preparation of milbemycin oxime and praziquantel (Milprazon 12.5 mg/125 mg tablets for dogs weighing at least 5 kg®) – 4 tablets were given to the lion, and 2 tablets were given to the cougar, both with small amount of food. A brown bear with ascarid infection was treated with a combined preparation of ivermectin and praziquantel (Noromectin Praziquantel Duo, 18.7 mg/g + 140.3 mg/g Oral Paste for Horses®) – 2 syringes were given with small amount of food. Control fecal samples were investigated to evaluate the effectiveness of the treatment on the 7, 30 and 60 day after the drug applications. Fecal tests of all three animals were negative on day 7 after treatment. They were negative on days 30 and 60 for the lion and bear. However, reappearance of *T. leonina* infection in the cougar occurred 30 days after treatment. Therefore, the cougar was given 3 tablets of another preparation, each of which contained praziquantel 50mg, pyrantel embonate 144mg and fenbendazole 200 mg (Cestal plus®, Ceva Animal Health, Bulgaria). No parasite eggs were found in the feces of cougar for 60 days thereafter. There were no adverse drug reactions in any of the three animals under study.

Conclusion

The following conclusions and recommendations could be drawn from the mentioned studies:

- Ascarid parasites are very persistent. Treatment once only after diagnosis is not sufficient to control them. Conventional deworming of the target animals four times per year is not sufficient too.
- Piperazine, pyrantel pamoate, benzimidazoles and macrocyclic lactones have been the most applied medicines to treat ascarid infections in lions, cougars and bears.
- Fenbendazole applying in extended schedules or a dosage of 15 mg/kg bw could be recommended for successful treatment of ascarid infections in bears.
- Ivermectin applying in a dosage of 0.2–0.3 mg/kg bw twice at four week interval could be recommended for successful treatment of ascarid infections in lions.
- Combined preparations of drugs from different pharmaceutical groups show the high efficiency against ascarid infections in lions, cougars and bears.

References

1. Alexander J., Khan S., Satheesh A. (2017). *Occurrence of Toxascaris leonina in captive lions at Thiruvananthapuram Zoological gardens*. The journal of Indian veterinary association, 15, 36–38.
2. Atanaskova E., Kochevski Z., Stefanovska J., Nikolovski G. (2011). *Endoparasites in wild animals at the zoological garden in Skopje, Macedonia*. Journal of Threatened Taxa, 3, 1955–1958.
3. Dehuri M., Panda M. R., Mohanty B. N., Sahoo N. (2013). *Prevalence and evaluation of anthelmintics against nematodes in lions (Panthera leo) of Nandankanan Zoo*. Journal of Wildlife Research, 1, 5–7.
4. Ganager D., Mamatha G. S., Muralidhara A., Jaya N. L., Shivashankar B. P. (2019). *Efficacy of oxcyclozanide and levamisole treatment on the gastrointestinal parasites in captive lions Panthera leo*. Journal of Threatened Taxa, 11, 15043–15046.
5. Kvapil P., Kastelic M., Dovc A., Bártová E., Cizek P., Lima N., Strus S. (2017). *An eight-year survey of the intestinal parasites of carnivores, hoofed mammals, primates, ratites and reptiles in the Ljubljana zoo in Slovenia*. Folia Parasitologica (Praha), 64, 2017.013.
6. Kumar A., Singla L. D., Singla N., Aulakh G. S., Singh J. (2005). *Management of piperazine resistance toxocariosis with ivermectin in lion (Panthera leo)*. Journal of Parasitic Diseases, 29, 156–160.

7. Mastacan D., Wagner G., Cociu M., Micu N. (1969). *Heavy infection of a polar bear (Thalarctos maritimus) with Toxascaris transfuga (Rudolphi 1819)*. Internationalen Symposiums uber die Erkrankungen der Zootiere (llth), Zagreb, May 14-18, 1969, 175–179.
8. Mirolyubov M. G. (1961). *Helminths of bears and their control in the Kazan Zoological Gardens*. Uchenie Zapiski Kazanskogo Veterinarnogo Instituta, 81, 141–144.
9. Moudgil A. D., Singla L. D., Singh M. P. (2014). *First report on molecular identification and fenbendazole resistance against Baylisascaris transfuga infection in Melursus ursinus (sloth bear)*. Helminthologia, 51, 262–268.
10. Moudgil A. D., Singla L. D., Singh M. P. (2016). *An issue of public health concern due to emerging drug resistance against Toxascaris leonina (Linstow, 1909) in Asiatic lions (Panthera leo persica)*. International Journal of Infectious Diseases, 45S, 105.
11. Panayotova-Pencheva M., Dakova V. (2022). *Parasite infections in carnivores from the Sofia Zoo, Bulgaria*. International Scientific Research Congress Dedicated to the 30th Anniversary of Baku Eurasia University, IKSAD Global, 1218–1223.
12. Panova O. A., Khrustalev A. V. (2020). *Ascarids infestation of captive big cats (Felidae) in zoos*. In: IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science, 548 072023.
13. Papini R., Cavicchio P., Casarosa L. (1994). *In vivo ovicidal effect of mebendazole on Baylisascaris transfuga eggs*. Revue de Médecine Vétérinaire, 1, 55–57.
14. Ponomarenko V. Y., Fedorova E. V., Ponomarenko A. N., Latvinsky K. M., Zhukovskaya A. A. (2017). *Helminth fauna and treatment of predatory animals in the zoo Feldman Ecopark of Kharkiv*. Scientific notes of the educational institution of the Vitebsk Order Badge of honor State Academy of Veterinary Medicine, 53, 32–36. (In Russian).
15. Sapp S. G. H., Gupta P., Martin M. K., Murray M. H., Niedringhaus K. D., Pfaff M. A., Yabsley M. J. (2017). *Beyond the raccoon roundworm: the natural history of non-raccoon Baylisascaris species in the New World*. International Journal for Parasitology: Parasites and Wildlife, 6, 85–99.
16. Sayid A., Mohammed B. (1997–1998). *Prevalence and treatment of Toxascaris leonina in naturally infected carnivores in old Khartoum Zoo*. Sudan Journal of Veterinary Research, 15, 31–38.
17. Sheikh M. M., Tak H., Fazili M. F., Bhat B. A., Wani I. N. (2018). *Baylisascaris transfuga: a parasite with zoonotic potential*. International Journal of Scientific Research and Management, 3, 174–180.
18. Shuleshko O. O., Zhorina L. V., Rybalka M. A. (2017). *Nematodosis in brown bears and their treatment in zoos*. Science and technology bulletin of SRC for biosafety and environmental control of AIC, 5, 77–80. (In Ukrainian).
19. Singh P., Gupta M. P., Singla L. D., Singh N., Sharma D. R. (2006). *Prevalence and chemotherapy of gastrointestinal helminthic infections in wild carnivores in Mahendra Choudhury Zoological Park, Punjab*. Journal of Veterinary Parasitology, 20, 17–23.